

Creating a Website for Chicago City's Crimes Using MongoDB

Rusul J. Alsaedi¹, Farah S. Kamw², Qasim S. Kadhim³

¹Al-Qasim Green University, Babil, Iraq.

²Kent State University, Kent, USA.

³University of Babylon, Babil, Iraq.

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 24 Feb 2024,

Revised: 19 Mar 2024,

Accepted: 21 Mar 2024,

Online: 21 Apr 2024

Keywords:

Database; NoSQL; MongoDB;
Website; Visualization; Chicago;
Crimes

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we worked on the data that is related to the crimes of Chicago city since Chicago is a famous, important and big city. In our research, we have created a website that allows the user to view all the documents in the database, insert new document to the database, delete one document from the database based on case number field in the document, and update existing document in the database. In addition to that, our website allows the user to search documents by year. Our website also provides some visualization tools to see some statistical information about the number of crimes that were happened each year in Chicago city. The aim of this research is to implement a prototype that visualizes some statistical information about the crimes that were happened in Chicago city from 2001 to present. The other goal behind this research is to design a NoSQL database by using MongoDB and to use the indexing method in MongoDB to provide the efficient queries that retrieve information from the database. Then, we have implemented seven types of queries using pymongo.py. These queries are as follow: new, find, update, delete, find by year, count by year, and count by arrest. Our database was too big since it contains about 6000000 documents.

1. Introduction

Chicago is a famous, important and big city, so in this research, we used a dataset about the crimes of Chicago city to create our database. The database is a set of data that is saved, organized, and reached electronically [1]. The database management system (DBMS) is the software that is used with the database, applications, and the end users to analyze and get data [1]. The purpose of DBMS is to administrate the database and create, update, define, and query the database also [1]. The database has many

types such as the relational database management system (RDBMS) that most of its systems use SQL (Structured Query Language) to query the database [2]. The relational databases arrange the data into one or more tables or relations, and each table in the database consists of columns and rows [2]. The columns are also called attributes, and the rows are also called records or tuples [2]. The table has a unique key that identifies each row [2]. The other type of the database is the NoSQL database.

Corresponding author:

E-mail addresses: rusul@uoqasim.edu.iq (Rusul), fkamw@kent.edu (Farah), basic.qasim.shakir@uobabylon.edu.iq (Qasim)

doi: [10.5281/gsjcs.2024.11004865](https://doi.org/10.5281/gsjcs.2024.11004865)

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The NoSQL database means non-relational or non SQL database [3]. It is usually used in the real-time web applications and big data [3]. There are many examples of the NoSQL databases such as MongoDB, CouchDB, GimFire, Redis, Cassandra, memcached, Hazelcast, HBase, Mnesia, and Neo4j [4]. In our research, we chose MongoDB to create our database. MongoDB is a NoSQL database that is an open source document [4]. It consists of collections that equalize to the tables in the RDBMS, and each collection is a set of MongoDB documents [5]. The document equalizes to the row/ tuple in the RDBMS [5]. The field in MongoDB equalizes to the column in the RDBMS [5]. Then, we used a website to show our results. The website is a set of related web pages; that is usually identified with a domain name, and it is published on one web server at least [6].

Therefore, in our research, we have created a website for Chicago city's crimes that allows the user to view all the documents in the database, insert new document to the database, delete one document from the database based on the case number field in the document, and update existing document in the database. Furthermore, our website allows the user to search documents by year. Our website also provides some visualization tools to see some statistical information about the number of crimes that were happened each year in Chicago city. The aim of this research is to implement a prototype that visualizes some statistical information about the crimes that were happened in Chicago city from 2001 to present. The other goal behind this research is to design a NoSQL database by using MongoDB and to use the indexing method in MongoDB to provide the efficient queries that retrieve information from the database. Then, we have implemented seven types of queries using pymongo.py. These queries are as follow: new, find, update, delete, find by year, count by year, and count by arrest. Our database was too big since it contains about 6000000 documents.

1.1 Paper Organization

We proceed as follows. We present the related work in section 2, and discuss the software description in section 3. Finally, we conclude in section 4 with a short discussion.

2. Related Work

Chang Glasgow et al. [7] in section 2 showed how to create a website, and the basics that every simple website is needed to be generated. They showed in their work how to set the style of the website, and how to create the template of it [7]. In addition to that, they showed how to edit the pages of the website [7]. In [8], they studied the 11 steps of the website creation to generate a successful website by starting from the low level study until reaching the advanced study of the website creation. Mike Garcia [9] showed how to create a simple webpage by using the basics and the principles of the HTML and CSS; also, he showed [9] how to insert paragraphs and images into a webpage. Sumitkumar Kanoje et al. [10] discussed the pros and the cons of MongoDB using in social networks since social networks are the biggest networks that are used recently, and they are needed very large storage of data. Therefore, they showed that MongoDB is good to be used in social networks in some points, and it is not good in other points [10]. Zhu Wei-ping et al. [11] tried to use the NoSQL database instead of the relational database, and compared between these two types of the databases. They showed that MongoDB (the NoSQL database) is more efficient than the relational database in terms of query big data [11]. Dipina Damodaran B et al. [12] explained the performance of the relational (MySQL) and non-relational (MongoDB) databases in the field of super market management system. Comelia GYORODI et al. [13] and Sushil Soni et al. [14] tried to study the comparison between the relational and non-relational databases by choosing MySQL as an example of the relational database and MongoDB as an example of the non-relational database. Also, they showed in their study that MongoDB is more efficient than MySQL database [13] and [14].

Our paper is totally different from all the previous papers. We have created a website for Chicago city's crimes by using MongoDB. This website allows the user to view all the documents in the

database, insert new document to the database, delete one document from the database based on the case number field in the document, and update existing document in the database. In addition to that, our website allows the user to search documents by year. Our website also provides some visualization tools to see some statistical information about the number of crimes that were happened each year in Chicago city. The aim of this research is to implement a prototype that visualizes some statistical information about the crimes that were happened in Chicago city from 2001 to present. The other goal behind this research is to design a NoSQL database by using MongoDB and to use the indexing method in MongoDB to provide the efficient queries that retrieve information from the database. Then, we have implemented seven types of queries using pymongo.py. These queries are as follow: new, find, update, delete, find by year, count by year, and count by arrest. The interesting point is our database was too big; it contains about 6000000 documents.

3. Software Description

We have got our idea from the fact that Chicago is implementing the idea of big data city. Also, since Chicago is an important city, it was a good idea to investigate the level of crimes in that city.

In this research, we have downloaded the crimes dataset [15]. Our dataset is too big (it is about 6000000 records, and each record represents one crime with 22 fields). We used MongoDB to create a database called Project, which contains one collection with 5940000 documents (one document for each crime). To improve the performance of the queries, we have created two indexes in addition to the default index. The first one is based on the case number field, and the second one is compound index which is based on (Year and Arrest fields). The following figures show our project.

Figure 1: the home page of our website which contains several links (each one for one function).

Figure 2: the new page which allows the user to add one document to the database.

Figures (3 and 4) show the edit page that allows the user to edit specific document from the collection. This page asks the user to enter the case number; then, the system will automatically find and return that document from the collection; after that, it shows the values of all variables of that document. The user can modify the values and submit the changes to the system to update the document.

Figure 3: edit page.

Figure 6: the result of the query by year.

Figure 4: edit page (with values).

Figures (5 and 6) show the query by year page. In this page, the user enters the specific year in the year text box and click the submit button. The system will show a table which contains all the crimes that were happened in the input year.

Figure 7 shows statistical visualization page that shows an interactive bar chart for the number of crimes that were happened each year in Chicago city from 2001 to present. In the bar chart, the x-axis represents the year, and the y-axis represents the number of crimes.

Figure 7: number of crimes each year.

Figure 5: query by year.

Figures (8 and 9) show the grouped and stacked bar chart which can be used to do the comparison between the number of crimes and number of arrested criminals per year in Chicago city. These two visualization tools are interactive (the name and the value of each bar can be shown by moving the mouse over the bars).

Figure 8: grouped bar chart.

Figure 9: stacked bar chart.

The interesting point is our database was too big since it contains about 6000000 documents; this makes the work interesting by trying to improve the performance of the queries by doing multiple types of indexing for the database. Also, the results of the queries were very interesting; for example, in one query, we have found that the number of crimes each year is too big compared with the number of arrested criminals.

4. Conclusion

In this research, we worked on the dataset of the crimes of Chicago city since Chicago is an important and big city. As a result, we have created a website that allows the user to view all the documents in the database, insert new document to the database, delete one document from the database based on the case number field in the document, and update existing document in

the database. Furthermore, our website allows the user to search documents by year. Moreover, our website provides some visualization tools to see some statistical information about the number of crimes that were happened each year in Chicago city. The first aim of this research is to design a NoSQL database by using MongoDB and to use the indexing method in MongoDB to provide the efficient queries that retrieve information from the database. Then, we have implemented seven types of queries using pymongo.py. These queries are as follow: new, find, update, delete, find by year, count by year, and count by arrest. The other goal behind this research is to implement a prototype that visualizes some statistical information about the crimes that were happened in Chicago city from 2001 to present.

For future work, we are going to add more queries on the crimes database. Also, we are going to use other visualization methods to visualize the results of the queries. For example, we are going to use the heat-map to show the crimes that were happened in each location in Chicago city based on the latitude and longitude fields that we have in our database.

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